

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL OPERATION OF PISTON COMPRESSORS

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Abstract

In article the analysis of existing system of cooling of GMC installed on or BCS and practical reasons of occurrence of complications in system of cooling leading to loss of productivity and difficult technical drawbacks are given. To eliminate the shortcomings in the cooling system the authors propose a new design of refrigerators, capable structurally and technologically to eliminate the practical defects in the cooling system of GMC.

Keywords: compressor gas lift, oil and gas field equipment, process system, compressor unit, process parameters, field oil pipelines, gas lift or booster compressor station, tubing, field gas separation station, compressed gas, piston compressor, offshore oil and gas condensate fields.

Energy is the key to life in the 21st century.

In this aspect, oil and gas production plays an important role in the energy system. The main link in development of oil and gas or gas condensate field is creation of rational technological system "production, collection, preparation and transportation" of extracted products (oil, gas, water, mechanical impurities) and effective placement of oil and gas production equipment.

The system of "production, gathering, preparation and transportation" is called a set of physical sub-objects for realization of a particular technological process. And the process itself consists in the finite area "oil and gas reservoir - drilling - well operation - well-head - collection, preparation and transport of products to the consumer" with definite boundaries.

The system is characterized not only by its field boundaries. Also, it affects technological parametric properties of the produced product and internal energy.

Therefore, oil and gas field equipment selected by design should ensure normal operation of oil and gas wells, both in the process of flowing and at mechanical impact into borehole bottomhole zone.

Wide introduction of compressor gas-lift method enables to intensify oil and gas production, improve efficiency of treatment and utilization of associated petroleum gas and oil from oil and gas fields, including offshore fields.

In the SOCAR system, compressor gas-lift oil and gas production is applied in all oil and gas production directorates operating offshore oil and gas condensate fields.

In field practice continuous compressor gas lift is characterised by high technical and economic efficiency, absence of mechanisms and rubbing parts in oil wells, simple maintenance and regulation of technological mode of each well.

Technological process of oil and gas production by compressor gas-lift method consists mainly in operation and maintenance of wells, technological equipment and installations, gas distribution system, compressor units installed at gas-lift or booster compressor stations (GCS or BCS), belonging to oil and gas production industry.

It is clear that the normal production activities of the whole complex of technological processes in the field of oil and gas compressor gas-lift method can be implemented only on the basis of oil and gas fields equipped with highly efficient equipment. In this regard, improvement of the existing system "compressor gas-lift production, collection, treatment and transportation of products" by improving the efficiency of each equipment oil and gas wells and high-quality collection of information on the technological parameters of the whole system, including compressor units, allowing reliable analysis and rational adjustment of the process of oil and gas are highly relevant[1].

In field practice, in the process of operation of gas-lift oil and gas wells, technological parameters often change. This is due to changes in geological and technological state of the reservoir, hence in the bottomhole. It should be noted here that the study of technological parameters is connected with both technological operations of gas-lift wells in order to determine the production possibilities of the fields, and development and analysis of production, which predetermine both the initial and the current state of geological, technological and technical-economic information.

In this aspect, a single inseparable system of oil and gas production fields includes the following components:

Fig. 1.

1-Plant; 2-gas-lift oil and gas wells as sources of production; 3-wellheads; 4-well discharge lines for transportation to the primary production treatment facility; 5-processing unit; 6-oil and gas gathering station (OGGS); 7-pipeline network for simultaneous transportation of production of several wells to the offshore oil and gas gathering station (OGGS); 8-MOGGS; 8.1. - Oil field pipelines for oil transportation to the processing facility (CGS); 8.2. - Gas field pipelines for transportation of low pressure associated gas to the gas gathering station (GGS); 8.3.-productive gas pipelines for transport of natural or associated high-pressure gas; 9-field gas pipelines for transport of low-pressure associated gas from the GGS to the GCS or BCS; 9.1-GCS or BCS; 9.2-field gas pipelines for transport of compressed associated gas to gas-lift wells; 10-gas pipeline for transport of compressed high-pressure associated gas to a gas-processing plant; 11-gas pipeline for transport of dry gas after its processing to the consumer.

In order to create an optimum gas pressure at the wellhead before it is directed to the bottomhole to lift the product up, it must be remembered that this pressure can provide a given production rate. Therefore, a gas lift or booster compressor station (GCS or BCS) must continuously supply gas lift oil wells with compressed gas at the set optimum operating pressure. The full load to provide the entire gas lift system with compressed gas, however, falls on the gas engine piston compressors (GMC), which are installed at the GCS or BCS.

As practice shows, for all time of operation of GMC, conditions of work of units, especially in sea conditions, do not completely correspond to technical

conditions of operation of these units specified in specifications of the manufacturer and productivity actual decreases that does not allow to define concretely necessary quantity of GMC, for installation on GCS or BCS.

On the basis of the saved up long-term experience of GMC operation in systems of gas-lift and transport of associated petroleum gas low pressure which passes from the technological point of view in extremely heavy field conditions, it is established that indicators of GMC operation in uniform system of gas-lift and gas transport, technologically are interconnected (fig.2).

Fig. 2. Technological scheme of oil well operation in compressor gaslift system

Fig. 2 shows the process flow diagram of gas lift system of oil wells operation, where one of the main equipment is gas lift system installed on a gas compressor station or a booster compressor station.

As can be seen from technological scheme, during exploitation of gas-lift oil wells the production extracted from borehole bottom 1 goes through tubing 4, flowing valve 5 and discharge line 6 to the field primary treatment facility, where with help of oil-gas separator

7 separation into liquid (oil, water, mechanical impurities) and associated gas takes place.

The liquid via line 9 is directed to an oil treatment unit, and associated petroleum gas via field pipeline 8 with a pressure of 1.1÷1.2 MPa is directed to a field gas separation unit 10 and, having passed there a 2-stage separation preparation, is transported at a distance of 25-35 km to the head gas separator 11 of a GCS or BCS via field pipeline 8. The low-pressure associated petroleum gas after treatment at the head gas separator is directed to a gas compressor station or booster compressor station 12, where the gas is pressurized to the pressure of 3.5÷3.7 MPa for one gas-lift system or to the pressure of 7.5÷7.8 MPa for another gas-lift system. Up to 10 GMC are installed on each GCS or BCS according to the field's compressed gas demand.

The associated gas compressed to the required pressure is transported by the high-pressure gas main 13 to the gas distribution station 14 and from there after metering via distribution pipelines (distribution pipeline) 15 is delivered to the well 1. The gas, compressed with the required pressure, enters the inter-tube space between the first 4 and the second 3 tubing and flows into the production string 2, where it enters the bottomhole and degases the liquid. The degassed production from the bottom hole is lifted up by the riser pipes 4 and through the Christmas tree fittings 5 is directed to the discharge line 6 of the well and the closed cycle is repeated.

Thus, this technological process runs continuously during the whole period of field development by means of gaslift method till the next stage of oil production replacement by other mechanized methods.

It should be noted that regardless of the conditions of GMC operation in gaslift and associated petroleum gas transport systems in offshore conditions, these compressors must meet such parameters as performance, reliability, safety, processability and economy.

Despite the common operational characteristics of two different gas-lift systems in terms of pressure and compressed gas consumption, when producing oil from gas-lift wells, a number of geological, technological and technical complications in the reservoir, and consequently in the bottomhole 3, constantly appear, which leads to complications in the work of the gas-lift system.

Having studied works of many authors in the field of gas-dynamic calculation of reciprocating compressors, including their productivity, which in the last years was published countless number, we found out that nowhere were considered real processes taking place in compressor units especially of the 1st stage and in power cylinders of GMC working in gas-lift and low-pressure transport systems with frequently changing technological parameters, connected with cooling system of both working medium and compressor cylinders, power cylinders, etc.

Therefore, it is difficult to overestimate the importance of careful study and understanding of the real gas-dynamic process occurring in cooling systems of reciprocating compressor units during gas compression on the stages and lubrication systems from the normal operation of which the productivity and power consumption of gas compressor units as a whole depends completely.

In field practice failure in systems of cooling of GMC installed in GCS or BCS always leads to decrease in productivity of compressor units and increase in technical defects especially in cylinder-piston group, both in the power part and in a compressor part [4].

After a long study of the operation of gas-lift gas compressor units, the authors summarized the averaged practical values of the efficiency of gas-lift gas compressor system (and its parts), combined for the conditions of two NGDU SOCAR, shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Averaged values of the efficiency coefficients of the GMC in the compressor gaslift system

O/N	Link coefficients	GCS or BCS in the gas lift system
1	Full power output when compressed gas gas engine, η_{ge}	0,91
2	Gas Engine Piston Compressor (compressor part GM), η_{GMC}	0,75
3	Field gas pipelines, η_{fg}	0,2
4	Gas distribution stations, η_{gds}	0,1
5	Distribution pipelines, η_{dp}	0,1
6	Gas lift oil well, η_w	0,7
7	The whole compressor gas lift system η_{cgs}	0,5-0,6

Analysis of Table 1. The analysis of Table 1 reveals two ways of improving the efficiency of oil and gas production by the gaslift compressor system:

1. Increasing the efficiency of cooling of power and compressor cylinders according to the manufacturer's specifications, cooling of inter-stage compressed gas and lubrication systems and reducing intermediate unforeseen downtime of the GMC due to interruptions in cooling systems;

2. Increasing the efficiency of specific power consumption by the gas-compression unit to compress 1 kg of associated petroleum gas and the technical and economic performance of the gas-compression unit in a continuous cycle of gas-lift and gas transport systems.

As it is known in Azerbaijani oil company's system the following cooling systems are provided by the design for normal operation of a gas compressor station or booster station (Fig.3)

- Cooling of power cylinders with softened water according to the manufacturer's data sheet. However, due to the lack of softened water in offshore conditions, the design solution envisages the use of ordinary potable water, in which during operation of the GMC, scale is deposited in the power cylinder jackets, resulting in the heating of the power cylinders;

- cooling of compressor cylinders without necessary treatment by seawater at a temperature of no more than 5-10° C in autumn and winter and no more than 15-

17°C in spring and summer. During operation, compressor cylinder jackets become contaminated and deposits of barnacles, algae and other mechanical impurities occur. As a result the flow in the jackets is greatly reduced and the flow of the next amount of cooling seawater is reduced. As a result the compressor cylinders become much hotter than indicated on the data sheet and output is reduced.

- cooling in the coolers of the compressed low-pressure associated gas in the compressor cylinder

stages, on which the capacity of the entire GMC depends to a large extent.

- cooling in the coolers of lubricating oil according to the requirement of the technical specifications of the manufacturing plant, on which the elimination of technical defects, especially the wear of rubbing parts and units and their premature failure depends.

Fig. 3. Typical layout of communication and coolant supply for one GMC or GCS-BCS
1 - oil pump; 2 - oil cooler; 3 - power cylinders; 4 - gas cooler; 5 - gas collector; 6 - stage I compressor cylinders; 7 - stage II compressor cylinders

At present, the State Oil Company of Azerbaijan Republic operates more than 200 GMC of different modifications with the total capacity of more than 220 MW in gas lift, underground gas storage and transportation systems. Therefore, the issue of efficiency enhancement and development of new high-efficiency refrigerators for compression-associated low-pressure associated gas cooling system and its transportation for field needs with the use of GMC is of extreme urgency [5].

Long-term investigations of the cause of failure of several existing cooler designs show that when the coolant passes through the zigzag space between the tubes, dirt quickly accumulates, the area of the coolant passage decreases and consequently the cooling surface decreases. The reason here is that the flow velocity of

the cooling water changes to laminar mode and the volume of stagnant water increases and the area of the cooling water passage gradually becomes clogged.

Having studied these drawbacks the authors have suggested a completely different design of the cooler which allows to eliminate sedimentation of barnacles, algae and other mechanical impurities by maintaining constant turbulent mode and speed of spiral flow of cooling water.

The authors developed a new design of heat-exchange apparatus distinguished by both simple construction and intensive cooling of compressed hot gas due to use of natural cooling of sea water [2].

This design also differs from counterparts by simplicity of maintenance in field conditions and high operational reliability.

Laboratory research of manufactured small-size sample of new design maximally approximated in field

conditions initially showed satisfactory technological indicators.

Conclusions

1. Having studied practically for many years the operation of GMC cooling system installed on GCS or BCS and operated in the system of gaslift operation of offshore oil and gas wells, it has been established that the existing cooling system is far from being effective due to frequent occurrence of defects and reduction of cooling surface of coolers, consequently stopping refrigerating units;

2. For increase of refrigerators efficiency and considerable decrease of their stoppage due to defects the new design of refrigerators has been offered and agreed upon by field workers for its further development of drawings and manufacturing of a pilot prototype.

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